

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN BUNION DEFORMITY AND Q ANGLE IN HIGH-HEEL WEARING FEMALE OFFICE WORKERS IN LAHORE

Kalsoom Noor^{*1}, Samara Shaukat², Maheen Fatima³, Urooj Fatima⁴,
Saifeldin Hamed Siddig Mohamed⁵^{*1,3,4,5}Student Superior University, Lahore²Lecturer Superior University, Lahore¹kalsoomnoor76@gmail.com, ²samara.shaukat@superior.edu.pk, ³mahi78412@gmail.com, ⁴arooj5075@gmail.com, ⁵saf20109@gmail.comDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15962461>**Keywords**

Female, Foot Deformities, Hallux Valgus, High-Heeled Shoes, Occupational Health, Posture, Q Angle

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Corresponding Author: *

Kalsoom Noor

Abstract**Background**

Wearing high heels is linked with Q angles and risk of bunion deformity. Female office workers are affected due to prolonged use of such footwear. Existing studies suggest a biomechanical relationship between altered knee alignment and foot deformities caused by high-heeled shoes.

Objective

To determine the relationship between bunion deformity and Q angle in high heel wearer females.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted on 80 participants. Data was collected from female workers with unilateral hallus valgus deformity at al rafay foundation by using non probability convenience sampling technique. Measurement was done by using Manchester scale for bunion deformity and goniometer for measuring Q angle.

Result

The findings showed the mean age of 28.51 ± 6.90 years. The Q angle measured using a goniometer ranged from 5.30° to 24.70° , with a mean of $14.59 \pm 5.61^\circ$. Based on Q angle classification, 22.5% of participants had a decreased Q angle ($<10^\circ$), 35.0% had a normal Q angle ($10^\circ-15^\circ$), and 42.5% had an increased Q angle ($>15^\circ$). Regarding bunion deformity, 30.0% of participants had no deformity, 10.0% had mild, 28.7% had moderate, and 31.3% had severe deformity. A statistically significant association was found between bunion deformity and Q angle category (Chi-square test, $p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

Based on these findings it was concluded that there was a relationship between bunion deformity and Q angle in high heel wearer females.

INTRODUCTION

Hallux valgus, commonly referred to as bunion deformity, is a progressive musculoskeletal condition characterized by lateral deviation of the hallux and

medial prominence of the first metatarsal head. This deformity alters the biomechanics of the forefoot, often resulting in pain, impaired gait patterns, and

reduced functional mobility (1). Epidemiological data suggest that the condition is notably prevalent among women and older adults, with a reported prevalence of 23% among adults aged 18 to 65 years, increasing to approximately 36% in those over the age of 65 (2). Females are disproportionately affected, with a female-to-male ratio of approximately 4:1, which is largely attributed to footwear-related and biomechanical factors (3).

One of the most significant extrinsic risk factors associated with Hallux valgus is the prolonged use of high-heeled footwear, particularly among working women. (4) High heels elevate the rearfoot and shift the body's center of gravity anteriorly, thereby increasing plantar pressure over the forefoot and the first metatarsophalangeal joint (5). This excessive mechanical loading leads to structural strain and, over time, contributes to lateral deviation of the great toe (6). Shoes with restricted toe space further exacerbate joint malalignment, especially when high-heeled shoes are worn during early adulthood—a period when osseous structures are more malleable and susceptible to deformity (7). Barnes et al. (2024) reported that females who frequently wear high heels are 2.5 times more likely to develop bunion deformities than those wearing flat footwear. Furthermore, data from the United Kingdom indicate that 64% of women regularly wear high heels, placing them at elevated risk. (8)

Recent literature has also highlighted the potential association between proximal lower limb alignment—specifically the quadriceps angle (Q angle)—and the development of Hallux valgus. The Q angle is defined as the angle formed between a line drawn from the anterior superior iliac spine (ASIS) to the center of the patella, and a second line from the patella to the tibial tuberosity, reflecting the alignment of the femur and tibia (9). An increased Q angle is associated with a range of lower extremity pathologies, including patellofemoral pain syndrome, anterior cruciate ligament injuries, and foot deformities, primarily due to its influence on dynamic lower limb alignment and kinetic chain mechanics (10).

Women typically exhibit higher Q angles than men due to a broader pelvic structure, which may result in greater medial deviation of the first metatarsal (11). Biomechanically, an increased Q angle may lead to

greater valgus loading and altered pronation mechanics during gait, promoting subtalar joint eversion and medial collapse of the foot arch (12). These changes impose abnormal stress on the forefoot and contribute to lateral deviation at the first metatarsophalangeal joint (13). The findings further support this association; individuals with Q angles exceeding 20° have demonstrated significantly higher risk of developing Hallux valgus compared to those within the normal range (14). Given that the Q angle reflects the anatomical relationship between the hip, knee, and foot, excessive pronation and internal tibial rotation may contribute to its increase, thereby influencing foot posture and function (15).

Previous studies have explored the relationship between hallux valgus and Q angle, gait, foot posture, and footwear. However, findings on the impact of high heels on Q angle remain inconsistent. Most research lacks focus on occupational female populations, especially office workers. There is also limited data from Pakistani women who wear high heels regularly. This creates a gap in understanding the association between bunion deformity and Q angle in this specific group. The findings of this study may contribute to improved understanding of lower limb kinematics and inform preventive strategies, such as footwear recommendations, ergonomic workplace interventions, and early screening protocols. Ultimately, the study aims to support better clinical management, reduction in musculoskeletal pain, preservation of mobility, and enhancement of quality of life in this population.

HYPOTHESIS

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant association between bunion deformity and Q angle among high-heel wearing female office workers in Lahore.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant association between bunion deformity and Q angle among high-heel wearing female office workers in Lahore.

Methods

A cross-sectional study design was used to assess the association between bunion deformity and Q angle among female office workers. The study was

conducted at Al Rafay Foundation, Lahore, over a period of six months following the approval of the research synopsis. A total of 80 participants were recruited using a non-probability convenience sampling technique. The sample size was calculated using OpenEpiTool with a 95% confidence level (16). Female participants aged between 18 and 40 years with unilateral hallux valgus deformity, right-side limb dominance, BMI less than 30 and moderate to severe deformity on the Manchester Scale (score >2) were included (17). On the contrary participants with history of foot trauma, ulcers, or other foot deformities, congenital conditions such as clubfoot, chronic diseases, inflammatory conditions like rheumatoid arthritis, or neurological disorders including Parkinson's disease were excluded. (12) Those with a history of lower limb fractures, orthopedic surgery, leg length discrepancy or current pregnancy were also excluded. (18)

Manchester scale was used to assess bunion deformity and Q angle was measured by using goniometer. Manchester scale is a useful tool which is often seen to assess the severity of the bunion deformity. It has a grading range from none to severe. It reduces a standardise photographs to visually create the severity of the hallux valgus. Based on the severity is for the categorised into None, mild, moderate and severe. None shows grade 0, mild shows grade 1, moderate shows grade 2 and severe shows grade 3. It has a reliability range from 0.77 to 0.86. It also has a good validity range from 0.64 to 0.76. It has a sensitivity of 85% and specificity of 88%. (19) For assessing Q angle goniometer was used. Goniometer is an instrument that measures the available range of motion at a joint. It consists of three parts two arms and fulcrum which is at the centre. It further has two arms movable arm and stationary arm. (20) To measure the Q angle, each participant was positioned in a relaxed supine (face-up) position with both lower limbs extended and relaxed. The anatomical landmarks used for this measurement were the anterior superior iliac spine (ASIS), the center of the patella, and the tibial tuberosity. Using these landmarks, two reference lines were visualized: one from the ASIS to the center of the patella, and another from the center of

the patella to the tibial tuberosity. A standard universal goniometer was used for measurement. The **fulcrum** (axis) of the goniometer was placed directly over the center of the patella. The **fixed arm** of the goniometer was aligned with the line extending from the ASIS to the patella, while the **movable arm** was aligned with the line extending from the patella to the tibial tuberosity. It was noted that a Q angle between 1 and 21 degrees is considered normal; angles greater than 21 degrees indicated genu varum, while angles less than 1 degree indicated genu valgum. (21)

Results

The results indicate that the participants' ages ranged from 18 to 39 years, with a mean of 28.51 ± 6.90 . Their height averaged 5.47 ± 0.137 feet, ranging from 5.00 to 5.70 feet. The mean weight was 80.63 ± 9.59 kg, and values ranged from 50 to 81 kg. In terms of Body Mass Index (BMI), 36 (45.0%) females were in the normal range, while 44 (55.0%) were overweight. When examining the side affected by hallux valgus, 45 (56.3%) had the right foot affected, while 35 (43.8%) had left foot affected. Bunion deformity, assessed using the Manchester Scale showed 24 (30.0%) cases showed no deformity, 8 (10.0%) had mild deformity, 23 (28.7%) had moderate deformity, and 25 (31.3%) had severe deformity in table 1. The Q angle of participants, measured using a goniometer, ranged from 5.30 to 24.70, with a mean of 14.59 and a standard deviation of 5.61. Categorically, 34 participants (42.5%) exhibited an increased Q angle ($>15^\circ$), 28 (35.0%) had a normal Q angle ($10^\circ - 15^\circ$), and 18 (22.5%) showed a decreased Q angle ($<10^\circ$) in table 2. A significant association was identified between bunion deformity and Q angle category ($p < 0.05$) in table 3. Females with severe bunion deformity had a higher prevalence of increased Q angle, indicating a potential relationship between the severity of hallux valgus and abnormal Q angle alignment. This finding suggests that Q angle may play a contributing role in the progression or severity of bunion deformity among office workers.

Table 1 Bunion deformity (Manchester Scale)

Bunion deformity (Manchester Scale)	Frequency	Percentage
No deformity	24	30.0%
Mild deformity	8	10.0%
Moderate deformity	23	28.7%
Severe deformity	25	31.3%
Total	80	100.0%

Table 2 Q Angle Category

Q angle Category	Frequency	Percentage
Decreased Q angle (< 10°)	18	22.5
Normal Q angle (10°-15°)	28	35.0
Increased Q angle (> 15°)	34	42.5
Total	80	100.0

Table 1 Paired Samples Effect sizes

Chi Square Test, P=0.05

Bunion deformity (Manchester Scale) * Q angle Category Crosstabulation						
		Q angle Category			Total	P value
		Decreased Q angle (< 10°)	Normal Q angle (10°-15°)	Increased Q angle (> 15°)		
Bunion deformity (Manchester Scale)	No deformity	4	16	4	24	.005
	Mild deformity	3	1	4	8	
	Moderate deformity	6	7	10	23	
	Severe deformity	5	4	16	25	
Total		18	28	34	80	

Discussion

The aim of this study was to determine the association between bunion deformity and Q angle among high-heel-wearing female office workers in Lahore. The rationale behind this study was based on the increasing prevalence of hallux valgus in women who frequently wear high heels, yet limited research exists on its association with lower limb alignment, particularly in occupational populations. A cross-sectional research design was employed, and data were collected from 80 female participants selected through non-probability convenience sampling. Inclusion criteria included age between 18-40 years, right-side dominance, moderate to severe unilateral hallux valgus, BMI less than 30, and the ability to stand or walk independently. The

Manchester Scale was used to categorize bunion severity, and the Q angle was measured using a goniometer in a supine position to ensure standardization. Results of the study suggests that women with higher Q angles were more likely to demonstrate greater bunion severity. The data supports the hypothesis that altered knee alignment, indicated by an increased Q angle, may contribute to or result from biomechanical compensations associated with hallux valgus deformity. This is particularly notable in the context of high-heel wearers, where altered posture and forward weight shift may exacerbate Q angle widening and metatarsophalangeal joint strain. The findings of the current study support those of Kamil Yilmaz et al. (2025), who reported a positive correlation between

Q angle and hallux valgus severity, particularly on the right side. Like the current study, their cross-sectional design and use of the goniometer align methodologically. (22) The current study also aligns with Ezcan Tutus et al. (2024), who found a statistically significant relationship between Q angle, hallux valgus (graded by Manchester scale), and psychological variables such as body image. While our study did not assess psychological effects, the physical correlation with Q angle is consistent. (17) The findings of Wataru Kawakami et al. (2024), which indicated altered foot kinematics and posture in hallux valgus patients, are supported by this study's implication that bunion deformity may influence or be influenced by proximal limb alignment such as the Q angle. (23) On the contrary, Imam Akram et al. (2024) concluded that while high-heel usage increased the hallux valgus angle, it did not significantly affect the Q angle. The current study contradicts this by showing a strong association between high-heel wearers' Q angle and bunion deformity, suggesting that the duration or frequency of high-heel use or other biomechanical variables may account for the differing results. This discrepancy indicates the need for further study, possibly with controlled heel-use history and longitudinal design. (16) Additionally, Busra Sacli Eksilmez et al. (2024) found that women with moderate to severe hallux valgus had decreased foot function and physical performance. Although our study did not measure functional scores, the prevalence of overweight and severe bunion deformity in participants suggests potential limitations in mobility, reinforcing the need for early screening and intervention. (24) Similarly, Meiko Yokozuka et al. (2023) reported structural instability and medial arch collapse in HV individuals, which complements our finding of increased Q angle—suggestive of valgus knee stress and medial chain instability. (25) Based on previous evidence and the findings of the current study, it has been stated that a significant association exists between bunion deformity and Q angle in high-heel-wearing office workers. Despite providing valuable insight this study had few limitations. The sample was geographically restricted to Lahore and focused exclusively on a specific subgroup female office workers who wear high heels which may limit the

generalizability of findings to other populations. Additionally, heel-wearing habits were self-reported and not objectively assessed which may introduce recall bias. Moreover, the study did not assess functional or pain-related outcomes like gait disturbances or foot pain severity which might restricts the clinical applicability of the deformity classification and its biomechanical implications. Future research should address these gaps by incorporating dynamic and weight-bearing Q angle assessments to better represent functional biomechanics. The use of wearable sensors or digital tracking devices could enhance the accuracy of high-heel usage data. Furthermore, integrating functional measures such as gait analysis, pain scores, and balance testing would offer a more comprehensive understanding of how structural changes affect daily activities. Evaluating workplace awareness programs and ergonomic footwear interventions is also recommended to guide preventive strategies for populations at risk.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it was stated that high-heel-wearing female office workers in Lahore with more severe bunion deformity consistently exhibit larger Q angles. This association suggests a shared biomechanical pathway linking forefoot and knee alignment. Routine screening and early intervention targeting footwear habits and lower-limb mechanics are therefore warranted.

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